

Date Accessed (of search)	Search (Search term used)	Origin of website (e.g. Knowledge of Researcher; found in X)	(Primary) Website	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social)	High level finding (data we are interested in)	National; Regional or Cantonal	Experts Identified	Experts Note	New Website Identified	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social Care; Education; Youth work etc. See list)	Note	New Website Identified - Used as search?*
20.02.2018	BAG, Recht, Angehörigenpflege	Google Search	https://www.bag.admin.ch/bag/de/home/themen/strategien-politik/nationale-gesundheitspolitik/aktionsplan-pflegende-angehoerige.html	Government website, national health servic	Legal, health	Postulat eSeydoux-Christe (09.4199) «Ausreichend langer bezahlter Urlaub für Eltern von schwer kranken Kindern» Postulate der Kommission für soziale Sicherheit und Gesundheit des Nationalrates (13.3366): «Betreuungszulagen und Entlastungsmöglichkeiten für pflegende Angehörige» Bundesbeschluss über die Legislaturplanung vom 15. Juni 2012 mit der Massnahme 65: Förderung der Vereinbarkeit von Berufstätigkeit und Angehörigenpflege (Art. 18)	National			https://www.ekff.admin.ch/dokumentation/pflegen-betreuen-und-bezahlen/	Government website, national health servic			yes
21.02.2018	Postulat Seydoux-Christe (09.4199): Ausreichend langer bezahlter Urlaub für Eltern von schwer kranken Kindern	Google Search	https://www.parlament.ch/de/ratsbetrieb/suche-curia-vista/geschaeft?Affairid=20133366	Government website		Initiator and cosignatories of the Postulat 09.4199, so they seem to be sensitized as well as well-informed about family caring etc.	National	Lic. iur. Anne Seydoux-Christe Lic. iur. David Eugen Dr. iur. Urs Schwaller	Attorney and member of the Swiss Council of States (CVP Ständerätin, Jura) Attorney and former member of the Swiss Council of States (CVP Ständerat, St.Gallen) Attorney and former member of the Swiss Council of States (CVP Ständerat, Freiburg)					
21.02.2018	Postulat der Kommission für soziale Sicherheit und Gesundheit des Nationalrates (13.3366): «Betreuungszulagen und Entlastungsmöglichkeiten für pflegende Angehörige»	Google Search	https://www.parlament.ch/de/ratsbetrieb/suche-curia-vista/geschaeft?Affairid=20133366	Government website	-	Speaker of the national commission for social security and health (Kommission für soziale Sicherheit und Gesundheit-NR (11.411))	National	Silvia Schenker	Social worker and member of the Swiss Council of States (SP Nationalrätin, Basel Stadt)	-				
21.02.2018	Bundesbeschluss über die Legislaturplanung vom 15. Juni 2012 mit der Massnahme 65: Förderung der Vereinbarkeit von Berufstätigkeit und Angehörigenpflege (Art. 18)	Google Search	https://www.travaillsuisse.ch/themen/familie/pflegende_angehoerige	-	Advice website for carers	First national website for family caregivers	National	-	-	-				
20.02.2018	https://www.ekff.admin.ch/dokumentation/pflegen-betreuen-und-bezahlen/	Google Search	https://www.ekff.admin.ch/dokumentation/pflegen-betreuen-und-bezahlen/	Government website, national health servic	-	Publication - Abschnitt "Betreuung von pflegebedürftigen Betagten durch ihre Kinder:Übersicht über einige Gesetzesbestimmungen"	National	Prof. Dr. iur. Audrey Leuba	Prof. Dr. Leuba is a legal expert in family and civil law. She is also a member of Stiftungsrat Pro Senectute Switzerland and the national coordination-commission for family questions (EKFF). University of Geneva	-				
20.02.2018		Previous knowledge from university	http://www.rwi.uzh.ch/de/lehreforschung/alphabetisch/breitschmid.html	-	Legal, education children and young people	He is active in various commissions within the context of child and family law.	National	Prof. Dr. iur. Peter Breitschmid	Prof. Dr. Peter Breitschmid is an legal expert for child and adult protection law as well as for family law. University of Zurich	-				
20.02.2018		Previous knowledge from university	http://www.rwi.uzh.ch/de/lehreforschung/alphabetisch/michel.html	-	Legal, education children and young people	She worked for a legal service in the context of child and adult protection law. Dissertation "Rechte von Kindern in medizinischen Heilbehandlungen"	National	Prof. Dr. iur. Margot Michel	Prof. Dr. Michel is an legal expert for family law and medical law. University of Zurich	-				
20.02.2018		Previous knowledge from university	http://www.rwi.uzh.ch/de/lehreforschung/alphabetisch/buechler/person.html	-	Legal, education children and young people	She has published numerous articles in the in the area of tension between family law, ethics, medical progress, parental care and children.	National	Prof. Dr. iur. Andrea Buchler	Prof. Dr. Buchler is an legal expert for family law. University of Zurich	-				

20.02.2018		Previous knowledge from university	http://www.rwi.uzh.ch/de/lehre/forschung/alphabetisch/tag/bt/person.html		Legal, education children and young people	She is very active in the context of ethical decision within the context of law and medicine and has a well-founded interest in children and families.	National	Prof. Dr. iur. Brigitte Tag	Prof. Dr. Tag is an legal expert for criminal law, (bio)ethics and medical law. She is also the head of the Kompetenzzentrum Medizin - Ethik - Recht Helveticae (MERH). University of Zurich	-				
20.02.2018		Previous knowledge from university	https://www.webbw.ch/competence/people/biderbost_yvo.htm		Legal, children and young people	Member of working committee of KOKES (Konferenz für Kindes- und Erwachsenenschutz).	National	Dr. iur. Yvo Biderbost	Head of legal service at Kindes- und Erwachsenenschutzbehörde (KESB) der Stadt Zürich	-				
21.02.2018	young carers schweiz politik	Google Search	https://www.evivo.ch/web/evivo/news/_/asset_publisher/EQubLRg680NV/content/news_youngcarers_151124/10192	-	Advise website for carers		National	-	-	https://www.parlament.ch/de/ratsbetrieb/suche-curia-vista/geschaeft?AffairId=20153456	Government website, national health service	-	Postulate (15.3456): Pflegende Kinder nicht ausklammern	yes
21.02.2018	https://www.parlament.ch/de/ratsbetrieb/suche-curia-vista/geschaeft?AffairId=20153456	Google Search	https://www.parlament.ch/de/ratsbetrieb/suche-curia-vista/geschaeft?AffairId=20153456	Government website, national health service	-	Initiator of the postulate 15.3456. She seems to be sensitized as well as well-informed about children as caregivers and the legal context	National	Lic. phil I Barbara Schmid-Federer	Member of the Swiss Council of States (CVP Nationalrätin, Zürich)					
26.02.2018	Regula Ricka BAG	Google Search (previous knowledge Agnes)	http://careinfo.ch/de/aktionsplan-unterstuetzung-von-angehoerigen-mit-care-aufgaben/	-	Health, news website	Involved in several projects regarding family caregivers and their needs	National	Dr. Regula Ricka	Expert and lecturer at the BAG and the University of Basel for Health Science					
26.02.2018	Margreet Duetz BAG	Google Search (previous knowledge Agnes)	https://www.curaviva-zh.ch/files/T7VEDFJ/opt_r_3_langzeitversorgung_dsm_duetz_praesentation.pdf	National Health Service	-		National	Dr. med. Margreet Duetz Schmucki	Head of Sektion Nationale Gesundheitspolitik Bundesamt für Gesundheit					
26.02.2018	Gesundheitsförderung Schweiz pflegende Angehörige Mattig	Google Search (previous knowledge Agnes)	https://gesundheitsfoerderung.ch/ueber-uns/stiftung/mitarbeitende.html	National Health Service	-		National	Dr. iur. Thomas Mattig	Director of Gesundheitsförderung Schweiz and lecturer at the University of Geneva					
26.02.2018	Pflegende Angehörige, Perrig-Chiello Höpflinger	Google Search (previous knowledge)	http://www.hoepflinger.com/htop/ http://www.entwicklung.psy.unibe.ch/ueber-uns/personen/perrigchiello/index_ger.html	-	Health, Education		National	Prof. Dr. phil. François Höpflinger Prof. Dr. Pasqualina Perrig-Chiello		http://www.zeitlupe.ch/uploads/media/PS-Info_3_2014_DE.PDF	-	Health, news website	Potential expert (Dr. Salome von Greyerz) identified in this PDF will be used as a new search term	yes
26.02.2018	Dr. Salome von Greyerz	Google Search	https://www.bag.admin.ch/bag/de/home/das-bag/organisation/direktionsbereiche-abteilungen/direktionsbereich-gesundheitspolitik/abteilung-gesundheitsstrategien.html	National Health Service	-		National	Dr. Salome von Greyerz	Head of Health Strategies Division, BAG					
06.03.2018	dritti dei bambini ticino	Google search	http://www.aspi.ch/index.php?mode=308&lng=1&rif=4793a11c5e	NGO	Children and young people		Cantonal	Dr. med. Myriam Caranzano-Maitre Prof. Dr. med. Marcellina Mian	Executive Director of ASPI, member of the national board of the Swiss Foundation for Child Protection (www.kinderschutz.ch) and has developed the Foundation in the Italian part of Switzerland (www.aspi.ch). Pediatrician who has been working in child maltreatment prevention and medical education since 1975 in Canada, the United States and internationally.	http://www.gruppo20novembre.ch		Children and young people		yes
06.03.2018	http://www.gruppo20novembre.ch/	Found on http://www.aspi.ch/	http://www.gruppo20novembre.ch/		Children and young people		Cantonal	Reto Medici	Lawyer, Juvenile Magistrate of Canton Ticino, Lugano; President of the Demetra Association, Bellinzona; Member of the Board of Directors of the Pro Juventute Foundation, Zurich					
06.03.2018	Prof. Annie Oulevey	Google Search (previous knowledge Agnes)			Education		Cantonal	Prof. Dr. phil. Annie Oulevey Bachmann	Head of the institut of Health (HES) at the university of Lausanne					